

From Utensil Grasping to Food Transfer: A Learning-Based Framework for Robotic Feeding

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Abstract—Feeding assistance is a fundamental challenge in assistive robotics, requiring robust perception, adaptive motion control, and safe human–robot interaction. This paper presents a preliminary framework for autonomous robotic feeding, structured into three modules: utensil grasping, bite acquisition, and food transfer. The framework integrates visual perception with Learning from Demonstration (LfD), using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) for trajectory adaptation. Utensil grasping is achieved through affordance detection, food segmentation is performed using HSV-based color detection, and mouth localization is estimated with Mediapipe. Experiments conducted with a 6-DoF manipulator and RGB-D cameras show an overall success rate of 65% across complete feeding trials, with the highest reliability in utensil grasping (95%) and food transfer (85% given successful bite acquisition). Results highlight the bite acquisition stage as the main bottleneck due to limitations of color-based segmentation. Future work will address these challenges by integrating foundation models for robust food detection, expanding food variety, and incorporating user-in-the-loop interaction for natural bite selection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Feeding is a fundamental Activity of Daily Living (ADL) that directly impacts independence and quality of life. Individuals with mobility impairments often depend on caregivers, which increases reliance and workload. Robotic feeding assistance has the potential to restore autonomy while reducing caregiver burden.

Despite advances, autonomous feeding remains challenging as it requires robust perception, safe interaction, and adaptive motion control. The robot must identify utensils, acquire food, and transfer it to the user’s mouth under dynamic conditions.

In this work, we present a preliminary framework that integrates visual perception and Learning from Demonstration (LfD). The system detects utensil affordances, segments food using HSV-based color detection, and localizes the mouth with Mediapipe. Motion is adapted through Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), enabling trajectory generation conditioned on perception cues across the feeding process.

II. METHOD

In this work, we propose an initial framework for feeding assistance. This framework is structured into three main modules: **Utensil Module**, **Bite Acquisition Module**, and **Food Transfer Module**, which together enable the autonomous execution of an initial assistive feeding task. Each module combines visual perception with control based on *Learning from Demonstration* (LfD), using *Gaussian Mixture Models* (GMM) in the stages where trajectory adaptation is required

according to visual reference, as shown in Figure 1. Each module is described below.

- 1) **Utensil Module:** In this module, the system identifies the grasping point of the fork. RGB and depth images are used as input to an *affordance detection* model, which estimates the optimal position for grasping. Based on the predicted affordance point, a *GMM* is conditioned to generate the approach trajectory, ensuring adaptive motion to the actual position of the utensil in the environment.
- 2) **Bite Acquisition Module:** After the fork is grasped, the robot performs food detection. Fruits are identified using RGB and depth images, applying segmentation in the *HSV color space* to extract the centroid of the target fruit. This centroid is then used to condition the *GMM*, which generates the *bite acquisition* trajectory, allowing the robot to skewer the food accurately even in scenarios with positional variation.
- 3) **Food Transfer Module:** In the final stage, the system transfers the food to the user’s mouth. The mouth position is estimated in real time using *Mediapipe*, which provides 3D facial landmarks. Based on this information, the system performs direct trajectory generation (without using GMM) to safely and precisely deliver the food to an outside-mouth position (*outside bite transfer*).

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experimental Setup

The experiments were conducted on an assistive feeding task consisting of three stages: (i) grasping a fork, (ii) acquiring a fruit, and (iii) transferring it to the user’s mouth. This structure reflects the sequential nature of feeding assistance, where each stage depends on the successful completion of the previous one. The food items used in the experiments included banana, apple, tangerine, and grape, chosen to represent different shapes, sizes, and textures.

The robotic platform, in Figure 1, consists of a Trossen Robotics WidowX 6-DoF manipulator, used to perform the grasping and motion tasks. Visual perception is supported by two RGB-D cameras: an Intel RealSense D405, employed for utensil affordance detection and fruit segmentation, and an Intel RealSense D435i, used for real-time mouth position estimation through facial landmarks. Robot control was implemented using custom Python scripts for trajectory generation and execution, with Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) conditioning the motions on perception cues at each stage.

Fig. 1. (Left) Diagram of the system logic, with the three module implementations. (Right) Hardware system, with Mobile AI workstation.

B. Results

The results (Table I) indicate that the framework successfully completes the feeding task in 65% of trials. The highest performance was achieved in utensil grasping (95%), showing robust affordance detection and trajectory adaptation. The main bottleneck was bite acquisition (70%), where HSV-based segmentation was sensitive to lighting and color similarity, leading to occasional failures.

It is important to note that the 65% success rate in the food transfer stage was computed only for trials where the bite acquisition was successful. When considered independently of the previous stage, the transfer achieved 85% success (17/20). This suggests that, given a correctly acquired bite, the system is generally reliable at delivering food to the user's mouth. Therefore, end-to-end performance is primarily constrained by the bite acquisition module, highlighting it as the main area for future improvement.

TABLE I
SUCCESS RATE OF EACH STAGE OF THE FEEDING FRAMEWORK.

Stage	Success	Rate (%)
Utensil Module - Grasping the fork (affordance)	19/20	95%
Bite Acquisition - Acquiring the fruit	14/20	70%
Food Transfer - Transferring to the mouth	13/20	65%
Complete task (end-to-end)	13/20	65%

C. Discussion

The results reveal that the framework performs reliably in utensil grasping and food transfer, but is limited by the bite acquisition stage. The reliance on HSV-based segmentation

makes fruit detection sensitive to lighting and background conditions, which reduces robustness and constrains end-to-end performance. Nevertheless, the transfer stage showed high reliability when food was available, indicating that the perception module is the main bottleneck rather than motion generation. Future work should focus on replacing color-based segmentation with semantic object detection methods, which are expected to increase robustness and improve overall task success.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presented an initial framework for assistive feeding, structured into three modules: utensil grasping, bite acquisition, and food transfer. The framework achieved 65% success in complete end-to-end trials, with robust performance in utensil grasping (95%) and reliable food transfer given a successful bite acquisition (85%). The main limitation identified was the reliance on HSV-based color segmentation for fruit detection, which was sensitive to lighting and color similarity.

Future work will focus on enhancing the perception framework, particularly by replacing color-based segmentation with foundation models for food detection. Expanding the range of food items, integrating adaptive control strategies, and conducting user-in-the-loop studies will also be essential steps toward developing a reliable and user-safe assistive feeding system. Another important direction is bite selection, where user commands can be given directly through natural language with the aid of foundation models.